

**BARANGAY IMBAYAO RESIDENTS' PERCEPTION
OF THE MT. KITANGLAD RANGE NATURAL PARK**

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ACCEPTANCE SHEET

This Special Problem entitled “BARANGAY IMBAYAO RESIDENTS’ PERCEPTION OF THE MT. KITANGLAD RANGE NATURAL PARK” prepared and submitted by **Wilson John D. Barbon** in partial fulfillment of the requirements of ENRM 290 (Special Problem) is hereby accepted.

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ABSTRACT

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The establishment and management of protected areas have been considered an advancement of environmentalism. Protected areas are concrete expressions of humanity’s acceptance that human activities have resulted to the dwindling of biodiversity and natural resources threatening critical ecological services. Community perception towards the protected area is one factor in achieving both conservation and social development objectives. A positive perception will lead to higher level of support given by the community to park management activities. Likewise, a negative perception will lead to low level of community support. This study investigated the community perception of barangay Imbayao in Malaybalay City towards the Mt. Kitanglad Range Natural Park (MKRNP) in the province of Bukidnon, Philippines. Community perceptions were identified through a community survey involving 256 respondents representing the total number of households in the barangay. The results of the study revealed that the community perceptions of the purpose and benefits of the MKRNP are more aligned to the biodiversity protection goal stated by the MKRNP law. The community also perceived that creation of the park will provide them better social services and that it will create community pride of having the park. Based on the results it is recommended that an intensified information and education campaign (IEC) about the MKRNP is undertaken. The IEC must focus on the important role of community participation in park management to achieve not just biodiversity conservation but also social development of the communities. It is also recommended to intensify programs that will accrue benefits and incentives to communities for contributing in park management. This is important since community members have traded-off their access to farm lands within the park when it was declared as park.

Declaration

This is to certify that

- i the special problem comprises only my original work towards the MENRM except where indicated,
- ii due acknowledgement has been made in the text to all other material used,
- iii the special problem is fewer than 25 000 words in length, exclusive of tables, maps, bibliographies and appendices

WILSON JOHN D. BARBON

Date Signed

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ACRONYMS

MKRNP	Mount Kitanglad Range Natural Park
KIN	Kitanglad Integrated NGOs, Incorporated
PAMB	Protected Area Management Board
NGO	Non-Government Organization
NIPAS	National Integrated Protected Area System
PA	Protected Area
PASU	Protected Area Superintendent
DENR	Department Environment and Natural Resources
LGU	Local Government Unit
WB-CPPAP	World Bank-Conservation of Priority Protected Areas Project
NDLA	Non-Destructive Livelihood Activities
BMS	Biodiversity Monitoring System
CBFMA	Community-based Forest Management Agreement
KGV	Kitanglad Guards Volunteer
IP	Indigenous Peoples
PO	Peoples' Organization
NSO	National Statistics Office
CWM	Community-based Wildlife Management
ICDP	Integrated Conservation and Development Project

CHAPTER I: INTRODUCTION

The Mount Kitanglad Range in Bukidnon is a significant natural resource of the province. Ecologically, it is home for a wide variety of species of flora and fauna including the Philippine Eagle. Its headwaters drain into 21 rivers including the rivers of Tagoloan, Cagayan and Pulangi. The Pulangi River drains eventually into the Rio Grande de Mindanao in Central Mindanao. Socially, the mountain range is also home to three tribal groups in the province, the Higaonons, Bukidnons and Talaandigs. By virtue of this significance of the mountain range, it was declared as a national park in 1990 and eventually become one of the ten priority conservation and protection sites under the National Integrated Protected Area Systems Act. The natural park has a total of 40,176 hectares including buffer zones (Talamdan, 2000). The stated goals of MKRNP are laid down in the Republic Act (RA) 8978 the national legislation formally declaring the Mt. Kitanglad Range as a protected area and its peripheral areas as buffer zones. Section 2, the Declaration of Policy stated the purposes and reasons for protecting the Mt. Kitanglad Range. The Declaration of Policy stated as follows:

“Considering the importance of Mt. Kitanglad's unique biological resources and its aesthetic, economic and ecological importance, it behooves the State to undertake steps for its protection and preservation. It is therefore declared the policy of the State to ensure the protection and preservation of Mt. Kitanglad Range, the communities, their culture and way of life therein in accord with the rhythm and harmony of nature. In so doing, the State shall ensure the protection of biodiversity, sustainable and participatory development, and advance and protect the interests of its legitimate inhabitants and honor customary laws.”

Like any protected areas in the country, the establishment and management of Mt. Kitanglad requires both conservation and social development strategies. The relationship between conservation objectives and social development objectives are closely linked that non-attainment of either conservation or social development greatly affects the entire management and maintenance of the protected area. Community perception towards the protected area is one factor in the interaction of conservation and social development objectives. A positive perception will lead to higher level of support given by the community to park management activities. Likewise, a negative perception will lead to low level of community support. An example of community

support to protected area management is compliance of communities to park management regulations.

Barangay Imbayao in Malaybalay City is one of the barangays that falls within the buffer zone of the Mt. Kitanglad Range Natural Park. The barangay has received several social development projects from the Protected Area Management Board (PAMB) and non-government organizations such as the Kitanglad Integrated NGOs (KIN). The barangay is also subjected to pressure brought about by development such as the entry of banana plantation and poultry farms in the area. It is in this context that this study chose barangay Imbayao as an ideal location to investigate community perceptions of people subjected to conservation and social development strategies; social development strategies coming from the PAMB and NGOs and from large-scale economic ventures of the private sector.

Biodiversity conservation and natural resources management is not an exact science. The environment and human societies are complex systems. Conservation and natural resources management is treading into complex systems. Management requires adaptability and flexibility in order to achieve conservation and social development goals of the protected area.

Significance of the Study

The findings of this study are important contributions to the management of the Mt. Kitanglad Range Natural Park. This study could provide managers the knowledge on how the people along the periphery and within the buffer zones of the park perceived the purposes, benefits and the negative effects of the park and enables them to make necessary adjustments and improvements for effective information and education campaigns for community members. The findings of this study could add to the body of knowledge about the Mt. Kitanglad Range Natural Park to enable future researches on community perceptions in the other villages within and in the buffer areas of the protected area.

Objectives, scope and limitation of the study

This study has the following general objective:

1. to determine the perception of barangay Imbayao residents towards the MKRNP and if it is consistent with the stated objectives and intentions of the MKRNP.

Specifically, this study has the following objectives:

1. To characterize the socio-economic situation of barangay Imbayao;
2. To evaluate the community perception of barangay Imbayao residents on the purpose, benefits and negative effects of Republic Act 8978 or the Mt. Kitanglad Range Protected Area Act; and
3. To determine if age and educational attainment affect community perceptions

The scope of this study is one of the barangays within the MKRNP. This barangay is Imbayao of Malaybalay City, Bukidnon. This study investigated the community perception of the people of barangay Imbayao towards the MKRNP. The perceptions that the study focused on is on how the people perceived about the objectives and the benefits of the MKRNP. The data collection process to get the community perception is through a survey of all households in the barangay. The survey respondents were one adult representative of the 256 households of barangay. The collected data were subjected to basic statistical analysis methods. These methods are frequency distribution, percentages, averages and correlation techniques. The collected data are encoded using Microsoft Access software and analysis was made using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The limitations of this study are as follows:

- The number of communities covered is limited and it cannot represent the perceptions for all barangays within the MKRNP;
- There was no validation process with the community members to discuss the findings of the survey because of limited time and resources; and
- The researcher already limited the variables that influence perception to age and educational attainment instead of studying other variables.

Conceptual Framework of the Study

This study is anchored on the framework of community-based conservation which takes the two-prong direction of conservation and social development. According to this framework, community-based conservation approaches involve the tasks of (1) implementing more creative and multi-disciplinary approaches hence the

importance of participation and inclusivity of stakeholders as appropriate response to the complex interaction of social and ecological systems (Berkes, 2004); (2) establishing mechanisms that multiple stakeholders contribute to the management of the protected area (Wells et al., 2004); (3) identifying, negotiating and implementing tradeoffs between the interests and claims of multiple stakeholders (Wells et al., 2004), and (4) facilitating a positive and strong psycho-social-cultural attachment of communities to the natural environment (Bow and Buy, 2003).

Applying this framework in the MKRNP, this study investigated the perceptions of the members of barangay Imbayao, a small village community within the buffer zone of the protected area. As shown in Figure 1, there are two forces that affect the protection and management of the MKRNP. The first is the one driven by the law that laid down the legal mandate of the park. These legal mandates are the stated goals and objectives of the park and are mainly implemented by the Protected Area Management Board (PAMB) headed by the government Department of Environment and Natural Resources (DENR). On the other side of the force are the community perceptions of the purpose, benefits and negative effects of having the MKRNP. Community perceptions are important aspects of conservation as it determines whether community members have a positive attachment to the purpose and goals of the park and whether they see their contributions in achieving these goals and purposes. It is very important that community perceptions match the intentions of the protected area as according to the experience of the community-based wildlife conservation in Tanzania, (Wells, et al., 2004) where it indicated that a positive perception that the community benefited from wildlife conservation will likewise increase their support for conservation.

The stated goals and objectives as stipulated by law and the community perceptions towards the MKRNP are independent to each other. Although community leaders are actively participating in the PAMB and community members are attending activities initiated by the PAMB, it does not always follow that the communities have a shared view of the parks intentions and benefits. In this study, the community perceptions are divided into 3 areas. These are perceived purposes, perceived benefits and perceived negative effects of the protected area. The researcher also investigated two other factors are investigated, the age in years and the level of formal education attained, whether these are affecting the perceptions of the community members. These two factors were chosen because indigenous peoples in the MKRNP consider Mt. Kitanglad as sacred and a vital component of their cultural beliefs, practices and

survival. But according to many accounts of tribal leaders, this view of the mountain is slowly eroding as cultural beliefs and practices are slowly eroded with formal education of the younger generation of indigenous peoples.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

CHAPTER II

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The topic about the social aspects of natural resources management and biodiversity conservation has been a subject of many conservation scientists and practitioners. This chapter laid down the different literature related to key ideas and arguments on community-based conservation approaches, the involvement of key stakeholders and the relationship of people's perceptions towards the success and failure of natural resources management and conservation.

Perspectives in Community-based Conservation Approaches

Conservation approaches has evolved through the years from exclusionary conservation approaches-the fences and fines approach- to a more participatory, community-based approaches. However, community-based conservation approaches have led to mixed results and experiences that have led to debates on whether the goals of conservation and developments can go together or not. Two positions are emerging in this debate. One position is that the failure of conservation and development approaches is not because the concept is flawed but it is in the implementation of the concept that is flawed, especially with regards to the transfer of power and responsibility to communities. The other position believed that conservation and development goals are both important goals but they should be delinked because mixing them will not serve well either of the two goals (Berkes, 2004).

Community-based conservation approaches have emerged during the time when the concepts and paradigms of ecology and applied ecology are also developing and shifting. Berkes (2004) mentioned these three shifts are (1) the shift from the reductionist to a more systems view of the world, (2) the shift that now includes humans into the ecosystem and (3) the shift from expert-based approaches to participatory conservation and management approaches.

These shifts in the concepts on ecology and applied ecology have led to the emergence of multi-disciplinary approaches to conservation that greatly consider the complex integration of social and ecological systems. Participatory approaches in conservation work have gained popularity for two reasons. One is that the complex interaction of social and ecological systems requires a more creative and multi-

disciplinary approaches hence the importance of participation and inclusivity of stakeholders. Second is the emergence of strong civil societies and stakeholders brought about by changes in the post-modern age like globalization (Berkes, 2004).

The idea of communities in the context of community-based conservation has also taken a facelift (Berkes, 2004). According to the study, communities are not simple and isolated agents in the interaction between society and the environment. Communities are not isolated systems but are embedded in larger systems and they respond to pressures and incentives. Berkes (2004) prescribe that it will be useful to think of community-based conservation as environmental governance and as conservation action that starts from the ground up and entails cross-cutting interactions. In order to effectively ground conservation, one has to make a careful and correct understanding of the nature of people, communities and institutions.

Stakeholders' Involvement in Conservation

Wells and McShane (2004) explored the lessons from the many years of implementing integrated conservation and development projects (ICDP) in the world. They seek to answer the question of “how can protected areas and their supporters conserve biodiversity more effectively by engaging and working with local constituents or stakeholders?” Many projects that work for conservation and development are sometime based on unrealistic assumptions. One is the assumption that there are win-win strategies that achieves conservation goals together with economic development. Most of the time in these projects is how to identify, negotiate and implement trade-offs between the interests and claims of multiple stakeholders. One important finding they have is that although conservation and development projects are intended for the communities but rarely the decision on launching a conservation and development project is not made by the communities themselves. As a result of this, the gains from the implementation of project also rarely persist after the project term.

A major challenge in implementing conservation and development projects is developing effective mechanisms to engage local constituents or stakeholders. Stakeholders and constituents are those people whose livelihoods, interests and futures are linked to the interests and future of the protected area, as well as institutions with interests and jurisdiction in the protected area such as community-based organizations, local governments, and national government agencies with local responsibilities,

research organizations, schools and churches. The people concerned may be indigenous, recent migrants or a combination of these. (Wells et al., 2004)

Conservation and development projects need to support the engagement of civil society and a broader variety of stakeholders in protected area planning and decision- making. Projects should attempt to engage stakeholders more deeply in defining and formulating the objectives of the project, in monitoring progress, in learning from experience, and in systematically documenting and disseminating findings (Wells et al., 2004).

To make decisions involving multi-stakeholders, trade-off analysis has been demonstrated in marine protected areas as presented by Brown et al (2000). The tool includes steps such as stakeholders' analysis, criteria setting for social, economic and ecological objectives, scenario identification and subjecting these scenarios to the criteria set by the stakeholders. The tool was used in the Buccoo Reef Marine Park in Tobago (Brown et al., 2000).

Perception and Participation of Communities in Conservation

In a study conducted on community-based wildlife management (CWM) in Tanzania, Africa, it revealed that it is important that full participation of communities are needed for the program to succeed. It added that extra effort should be implemented to create genuine interest on CWM. The study also showed that conservation interests or perception can also turn to negative when communities realize the trade-offs of conservation in this case their access to wildlife and the opportunity for better incomes. Even if the overall conservation work resulted to economic benefits but once people sees that these benefits are not equally distributed in the community, people's interest in the program will also disappear (Songorwa, 1999).

The dynamics between perceptions and attachment of people towards the natural environment has gained interest as a field of study among social change and conservation scientists. A study conducted by Bow and Buys (2003), exploring the role of the natural environment in creating a sense of community, revealed that a strong sense of attachment of the community to the natural environment leads to stronger feelings of concern when the natural environment is threatened by destruction and damage. To quote a finding from this study that demonstrated the relationship between community perception and conservation action:

“Most of the participants held the perception that in order for them to be able to maintain a continuous relationship with the natural environment, the Council (this is the body that manages the protected area) and the local residents have to protect, nurture and preserve the natural ecosystem from any further environmental degradation. They wanted the Council to invest more time and money into the upkeep of these pristine areas. Their environmental values may have been influenced by their long history in the area, beliefs and experiences with the natural environment (Bow and Buys, 2003).”

Previous perception studies have positively correlated the level of formal education to positive perceptions towards conservation programs (Gillingham and Lee, 1999; Sah and Heinen, 2001; McClanahan et al., 2005; Allendorf et al, 2006; Anthony, 2007). One idea that explains why higher education can lead to positive perceptions to environment is the idea of “environmental literacy” first espoused by David Orr (Orr, 1992). He explained that ecologically literacy will make people “appreciate something of how social structures, religion, sciences, technology, patriarchy, culture, agriculture, and human cussedness combine as causes of our (environmental) predicament.” In a study in Nepal (Mehta and Heinen, 2001) demonstrated the role of ecological literacy where residents with formal education have more access to environmental awareness programs that park managers conducted showed positive perceptions to the park.

Most the literature related to the role of age as a factor that influence attitudes, perceptions and behavior towards the natural environment show that age is negatively correlated; meaning as the person increases in age the less is the concern of this person towards the environment. There are many explanations being offered by the literature but of the more frequently cited reason is based on the opportunity to enjoy the benefits. Older people will not live long enough to enjoy the benefits of conserving natural resources (Whitehead, 1991; Carlsson and Johansson-Stenman, 2000). Howell and Laska (1991) also demonstrated the opposite that young people exhibit more concern about the natural environment.

Another perspective in looking at age as a factor to differing perceptions is the “cohort effect” of age which looks at age as a specific generation and not as the age of

the individual person. Specific age groups may have different experiences, socio-economic status, cultural identities or socialization hence their perceptions are shaped not just by their age but also of their context (Vlosky and Vlosky, 1999).

CHAPTER III: STUDY AREA AND METHODS

Biophysical Characteristic of Mt. Kitanglad Range Natural Park (MKRNP)

The MKRNP is found in the North-Central part of Bukidnon Province. The MKRNP accounts for 17.55 percent of the province's land area. It has several peaks among which are the highest in the country. Mt. Dulang-dulang with an elevation of 2,938 masl is the second highest peak in the country. Mt. Kitanglad range is the source of important river systems of North and Central Mindanao which include the Cagayan, Tagoloan and Pulangi Rivers. The Cagayan River Basin covers approximately 1,471 square kilometers of mountainous terrain in northwest Bukidnon extending to the western portion of the Province of Misamis Oriental. The Tagolo-an River Basin covering a drainage area of 1,577 square kilometers in the northwest portion of Bukidnon and a portion of Misamis Oriental originates from the range traversing in a northwesterly direction. The Pulangi River traverses a southwesterly direction towards Central Bukidnon and Cotabato Province. The climate of MKRNP falls under Type III of the modified Corona's classification. It is characterized as having a short dry season lasting only from one to three months with no pronounced maximum rain period. MKRNP is cloud-covered throughout the year. Its temperature ranges from 27.7 degrees Celsius (January) to 24.6 degrees Celsius (June). The park has the highest rainfall in June and the month of March is the driest. Relative humidity varies from 71 percent in May to 86 percent in September. The soil type of the foot slope of MKRNP is clay and generally deep, and commonly has volcanic rocks. In areas of the park with high soil erosion, the soil layer is shallow. The soil is well drained and is acidic. In higher elevations of the mountain range, the soil possesses more organic matter due to low temperature. (Sumbalan et al., 2001)

A study conducted in the park revealed that there are six major types of habitat in the MKRNP. These are the lowland residual dipterocarp forest, mossy forest, grassland, fresh water, and wetlands. MKRNP is considered one of the protected areas of the country with the richest faunas many of which are considered rare and endemic. A total of 377 floral species are found in the park of which 74 are endemic. Of the 21 species of reptiles found in the park, 13 are endemic and of 26 amphibians, 12 are declared endemic. There are 159 known species of birds of which 62 considered endemic. At least 50 species of mammals are known to exist in the park of which 32 are endemic. Likewise, 114 of the identified 131 species and sub-species of butterflies

in the park are endemic. There 159 species of flora and fauna that are considered rare and endangered. The park has exceptionally high conservation value in terms of high endemism of the vascular flora. This includes the endangered rootless vascular plant. Likewise, the park has been reported to have the highest tree density ever reported in a tropical forest (Garrity, et al., 2001 cited by Sumbalan et al., 2001). Barangay Imbayao the community in this study is part of the MKRNP Buffer Zone where residents are allowed some livelihood activities.

Historical Timeline of the Establishment of the MKRNP

The establishment of MKRNP started in 1988 when environmental groups in Bukidnon campaigned to force government to act towards preserving the remaining forests of Bukidnon. This resulted in the imposition of a logging moratorium in the entire province. This moratorium stopped the operations of logging companies in Mount Kitanglad. The moratorium came late as most of the lowland dipterocarp forests have already been cleared by logging and upland dwellers clearing forests for agricultural production. Forest fires during the El Nino years (1982-83) contributed to forest destruction. Fires that reached the range summit burned more than 6,000 hectares of primary forest. Another forest fire in 1998 burned 300 hectares of grassland and forestlands.

In 1989, the Sangguniang Bayan of Sumilao through Resolution No. 32 series of 1989 initiated the proclamation of Mt. Kitanglad Range a national park in order to protect its socio-economic and ecological importance. On 14 December 1990, President Corazon C. Aquino signed Presidential Proclamation No. 677 making Mount Kitanglad Range into a national park under the administration of the Department of Environment and Natural Resources Regional and Provincial Offices.

The passage of Republic Act 7586 of 1992 made Mount Kitanglad an initial component of the NIPAS. This made the range as a natural park which is defined “as a relatively large area not materially altered by human activity where extractive resource uses are not allowed and maintained to protect outstanding natural and scenic areas of national or international significance for scientific, educational and recreational use”(Section 4(h), RA 7586, 1992). Finally, on 9 November 2000, Republic Act 8978 was signed into law. This Act declared Mt. Kitanglad Range in the Province of Bukidnon as a protected area and its peripheral areas as buffer zones. It specifies that

the total bounded area of MKRNP is 47,270 hectares consisting of 31,235.19 protected areas and 16,034.81 hectares as its buffer zone (RA 8978, 2000).

Socio-economic Status of MKRNP Buffer Zone Communities

The socioeconomic characteristics of buffer zone residents of the MKRNP was discussed mainly by the journal called TALAMDAN of the Kitanglad Integrated NGOs based in Malaybalay City. The socio-economic studies were published in the Talamdan issue for July-September 1998. The key highlights of the socio-economic study were as follows:

- There are eight municipalities and 28 villages (barangays) that are part of the MKRNP as shown in Figure 2: Map of the MKRNP. Earlier studies reported that 451 households are actual occupants of the buffer zone of the park with a total of 2,512 members composed of 52 percent male and 47 percent females. The residents of the protected area account for 4.86 percent of the total population of the 28 villages around the MKRNP. The average household size of the buffer zone occupants is 5.57 persons. The average number of years of tenure in the community of the buffer zone occupants is 20 years. Buffer zone occupants have a low level of formal education. IPs and the other occupants are very knowledgeable about their immediate environment. They are also literate of their own indigenous language, knowledge and practices in agriculture, health and natural resources management. The percent of buffer zone occupants with no formal education is 28.5%. Only a few of the occupants have high school education (4.4%), vocation or two-year college course (0.3%) and those with four-year college education (0.2%).
- Farming is the main livelihood activity of the park occupants. Root crops are widely grown followed by corn and coffee. Fruit trees, spices, sugarcane and abaca are also cultivated. Less than one percent of the occupants grow rice, tobacco and coconut. Livestock is also raised by at least 80% of the occupants, majority of them raise chicken and cattle. Those engaged in rattan gathering, weaving and bamboo strips for basketry account for only 28%.
- In terms of sourcing potable water, only 0.4% of the buffer zone occupants get drinking water from water faucets. The rest get it from rivers (24.8%), streams (20.6%), springs (11.8%), deep wells (4.4%), and flowing creeks (2%). A majority of the occupants (81.6%) say that there are no schools in their area. Health services are almost non-existent. Household income of the protected

area occupants averages at PhP 1,205 monthly based on the 1999 survey in nine buffer zone sitios.

- The Indigenous People that inhabit the mountain range are mainly Talaandig (60.1%), Higa-onon (23.5%) and Bukidnons (7.7%). Based on the 1998 Census and Registration of MKRNP occupants, there are 451 households with a total of 2,512 individuals. The Talaandig tribe is the identity embraced by the people of Lantapan and Talakag under the leadership of the late Anastacio Saway of Songco who was known as Datu Kinulintang in 1975 (Opeña, 1998). The Higaonon tribe was organized by a certain Ricardo de la Camara out of the Bukidnons in Malaybalay and other lowlands of the northern part of Bukidnon. Finally, the Bukidnon tribe is one of the original two tribal divisions of Bukidnon as early as 1889. The Bukidnons are those who inhabit the lowlands and the Manobos occupy the mountain peripheries. The Bukidnons of the protected area are those who remained to be known as such when the Bukidnon tribe was further subdivided into Talaandig and Higaonon. The tenured migrants account for 8.7% of the reported occupants of the protected area, mainly Cebuanos (4.4%) and Boholanos (2.7%).

Description of Barangay Imbayao, Malaybalay City

Barangay Imbayao has a total land area of 6,042 hectares in which 4,000 hectares are classified as alienable and disposable lands. The remaining 2,042 hectares are classified as forest lands. It is bounded in the north by Barangay Kapitan Anghel, in the south by barangay Mapayag, in the east by barangay Sumpong and in the west by Mt. Kitanglad. Figure 3 showed the location of Imbayao within the City of Malaybalay. The barangay is 15 kilometers from the city proper. The barangay can be reached by all types of vehicles but the most common means of transportation is through hired motorcycle known locally as *habal-habal*. Barangay Imbayao has 4 puroks and 2 sitios (smaller units than the puroks). The soil of the barangay is mostly loam. The climate is considered temperate. The loam soil and temperate climates makes the barangay very suitable for agricultural production. The hills and slopes are cultivated by farmers to corn, root crops, fruits and vegetables. Plantation crops are also grown within the barangay such as abaca, pineapple and mango. There are also several high value crops grown especially within the buffer zones of Mt. Kitanglad Range Natural Park. These crops are cabbage, carrots, bell peppers, baguio beans and potatoes. There are 4 poultry farms in the barangay occupying 32 hectares in Purok 1 and 5. (Barangay Development Plan 2004-2008)

The barangay has a total of 280 hectares that falls within the buffer zone of Mt. Kitanglad Range Natural Park. The 34.5 hectares of the buffer zone of the barangay is cultivated with high value crops. Part of the buffer zone area is also classified as wildlife sanctuary and heavily protected. There are production forests in the buffer zone are under the Community-Based Forest Management program of the Department of Environment and Natural Resources (DENR, Barangay Development Plan 2004-2008). The figure below shows the map of Malaybalay City, showing barangay Imbayao shaded in gray.

Figure 2: Location map of barangay Imbayao, Malaybalay City

Preparatory Activities

Before the actual gathering of data for this study, the study design, materials and methods were presented to the MKRNP-PAMB Executive Committee for their permission. The PAMB-ExeCom gave their permission to conduct the study provided

they will receive final copies of the study report to the PAMB and PASu offices so that they can use the findings in improving their strategies. Formal letters were also given to the City Mayor of Malaybalay City and the Barangay Chairman of barangay Imbayao to inform them of the data collection activity in the community. They were also provided with copies of the MKRNP-PAMB Resolution permitting the conduct of data collection in the barangay. The purpose of these coordination activities was to ensure coordination and safety during the actual data collection activities.

A tribal ritual was also conducted in barangay Imbayao for the data collectors. The tribal ritual ensured the participation of members of the tribal community in Imbayao as well as acquired the goodwill of the tribal leaders in the barangay.

Collection of Perception Data of Barangay Imbayao

The choice of Barangay Imbayao in Malaybalay City as the site of this study was driven by two major considerations. One, the barangay has received several social development projects from the PAMB and non-government organizations such as the Kitanglad Integrated NGOs (KIN). Second, the barangay was also subjected to pressure brought about by development such as the entry of banana plantation and poultry farms in the area. It is in this context that this study chose barangay Imbayao as an ideal location to investigate community perceptions of people subjected to conservation and social development strategies; social development strategies coming from the PAMB and NGOs and from large-scale economic ventures of the private sector.

The perception data of barangay Imbayao were collected using a questionnaire. Four barangay health workers served as enumerators of the study. The questionnaire included questions on the demographic characteristic of the respondent and questions on their perception of the MKRNP. The instrument was formulated in Cebuano to facilitate easier communication between the enumerator and the respondent. The entire household population of the barangay consisting of 256 households were included in this survey. The head of the household was the target for the interviews but due to the unavailability of the household head, the next adult member of the household was interviewed instead. The respondents were asked of their perception toward MKRNP on three areas, namely: on the essence/purpose of the MKRNP, on the benefits of MKRNP and on the negative effects of MKRNP. They were made to choose or “vote” on six specific items under each perception area. They may choose any or all of the enumerated items by simply checking the particular item chosen.

Data Encoding and Analysis

The data was electronically stored in Microsoft Access database. The electronic database allowed for easy encoding and retrieval of relevant information to be analyzed. The calculations of basic descriptive statistics such as frequencies, percentages and mean were made in Microsoft Excel software and the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The analysis of the data uses descriptive statistics methods such as frequency distribution and percentages. To determine the relationship of age and level of education to the perceptions, the researcher prepared frequency distributions of community perceptions according to the age of respondents and another frequency distribution according to the level of education.

CHAPTER IV:

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Socio-Economic Scenario of Barangay Imbayao Residents

This study made a complete enumeration of the 256 households of the barangay. The distribution of the respondents of the study according to purok and sex is presented in Table 1. There were more female than male respondents since they usually the ones left-behind during daytime as the male members of the family are usually out in the farms. Puroks 1 to 3 have more respondents since these puroks are considered the center of barangay activities where the key barangay facilities such as schools and health facilities are located. Puroks 5, 6 and 7 have the lowest number of respondents since they are located near the forest areas of Mt. Kitanglad range while Purok 7 is a newly-created purok of the barangay.

Table 1. Distribution of the respondents by purok. Barangay Imbayao, 2008

PUROK NUMBER	NUMBER OF RESPONDENTS		
	Male	Female	Total
Purok 1	8	45	53
Purok 2	26	30	56
Purok 3	15	32	47
Purok 4	16	16	32
Purok 5	6	13	19
Purok 6	19	12	31
Purok 7	4	14	18
Total	94	162	256

As shown in Table 2, most of the respondents in addition to being females, are also of adult age of 21-39 years old (N=135, 52.7%). Almost all of the respondents are also married (N=214, 83.6%). The household size of the respondents is between 1 and 5 (N=137, 53.5%). This number is the same as the figures of the census data of the barangay in year 2000 which put the average household size to 5.

Table 2. Demographic Characteristics of Respondents, Barangay Imbayao, 2008

DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTIC	FREQUENCY N=256	PERCENTAGE
Age Group		
Young adults (20 yrs old & below)	15	5.9
Adults (21 – 39 yrs old)	135	52.7
Middle age (40 – 59 yrs old)	88	34.4
Senior (60 yrs old & above)	18	7.0
Marital Status		
Married	214	83.6
Single	17	6.6
Widow/widower	13	5.1
Separated	12	4.7
Household Size		
1-5	137	53.5
6-10	102	39.8
10-15	17	6.6
Years of Residence		
1-10	100	39.1
11-21	52	20.3
22-32	60	23.4
33-43	31	12.1
44-54	12	4.7
55-above	1	0.4
Tribal Affiliation		
Bukidnon	60	23.44
Higaonon	3	1.17
Igorot	3	1.17
Manobo	5	1.95
Talaandig	24	9.38
Migrant	161	62.89

DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTIC	FREQUENCY N=256	PERCENTAGE
Educational Attainment		
College/vocational education	12	4.7
High School	76	29.7
Elementary	118	46.1
No Schooling	50	19.5
Occupation		
Business	9	3.52
Farm labor	4	1.56
Farmer	189	73.83
Govt employee	1	0.39
Private employee	2	0.78
Housewife/housekeeper	51	19.92

In terms of the number of years the respondents have stayed in barangay Imbayao, 100 (39.1%) of the respondents are residents of the barangay for 0 to 10 years. Very few of the respondents are residents for 30 years and above. Migration and inter-marriages with people from other barangays can be an explanation why most of the respondents are recent residents in the barangay. This can also be the explanation of the increase of population and the number of households in the barangay from year 2000 to 2008. The 2000 NSO census stated that the barangay has a total number of households of 209 and after 8 years it has increased to 256 households.

Most of the residents in barangay Imbayao are migrant settlers. Most of them originated from the Visayas. The remaining residents belong to the indigenous peoples who are affiliated with the Bukidnon tribe, followed by the Talaandig tribe. The Bukidnon tribe is the original tribe of Bukidnon which is divided to two major groups the Higaonon and the Talaandig tribes. Most of the Talaandigs are resident of MKNRP especially in the neighboring municipality of Lantapan, Bukidnon.

In terms of the educational attainment of the respondents to the study, most of the respondents have completed the primary level education. This is followed by those who completed secondary level education. Very few have entered or graduated a college course. Fifty of the respondents are considered having not completed any formal education. The location of the barangay is very far from the center of

Malaybalay City. Most of the respondents have completed primary education since it is free and the barangay have the facilities to accommodate its residents. The number of respondents able to finish tertiary is low since most of these schools are not available in the barangay. Families have to spend more if they send their children to get secondary and college education in the center of Malaybalay City.

Most of the respondents are engaged in farming (N=189, 73.8%). This is followed by those who stay at home as housekeeper or housewives of farmers (N=51, 20%). Very few are engaged in business and private employment. The indigenous peoples of Bukidnon are both farming and hunting tribes. They farm in the lowlands and they hunt on the slopes of Mt. Kitanglad range. The migrants who came to Bukidnon from Luzon and the Visayas are also farmers. This is one explanation why there is a higher number of farmers in Imbayao. Another explanation is that the barangay offers very few opportunities for employment other than farming. For those who are engaged in business and not on farming, most of the time their business is of running a small consumer store (sari-sari stores) or vending native food products and small quantities of fruits and vegetables.

Community perception of barangay Imbayao residents on the purpose, benefits and negative effects of the Mt. Kitanglad Range Protected Area Act

The stated goals of MKRNP are laid down in the Republic Act (RA) 8978, the national legislation formally declaring the Mt. Kitanglad Range as a protected area and its peripheral areas as buffer zones. Section 2, the Declaration of Policy stated the purposes and reasons for protecting the Mt. Kitanglad Range. The Declaration of Policy stated as follows:

“Considering the importance of Mt. Kitanglad's unique biological resources and its aesthetic, economic and ecological importance, it behooves the State to undertake steps for its protection and preservation. It is therefore declared the policy of the State to ensure the protection and preservation of Mt. Kitanglad Range, the communities, their culture and way of life therein in accord with the rhythm and harmony of nature. In so doing, the State shall ensure the protection of biodiversity, sustainable and participatory development, and advance and protect the interests of its legitimate inhabitants and honor customary laws.”

To summarize the declaration, the objectives of the MKRNP are the (1) protection of biodiversity, (2) sustainable and participatory development of the communities, and (3) protection of the interests of legitimate inhabitants and honoring their customary laws.

This section presents and discusses the results of analyses of data on the perception of the community on the essence or purpose of the MKRNP. The overall perception of the respondents will be discussed first and followed by the discussion whether age and educational level influences the perceptions of the community.

Presented in Table 3 are the results of data analyses on the perception on the essence/purpose of MKRNP. As shown, most of the respondents perceived that the MKRNP should be *For the protection and conservation of its forests and Off-limits to human activities*. Both of these items obtained 216 responses or 84.4% of the respondents. Next to these perceptions is the item *For the protection of its remaining flora and fauna*, 180 responses or 70.3%. Following closely is the item *A sanctuary for endangered species of plants and animals*, with 177 responses or 69.1%. The items *Off-limits to farming* and *Tourist destination* follow far down below, with response of 133 or 52% and 100 or 39%, respectively.

These results reveal that the respondents generally agree with what the government envisions to be the purpose of the MKRNP, as stated in its goals and objectives in the proclamation declaring Mt Kitanglad Range as a natural park. This implies that the community has accepted the whole idea of the MKRNP. This further implies that the IEC efforts of the government, NGO's, PO's and other concerned groups have been successful. The results also revealed a misconception by the respondents by ranking at the top the item *Off-limits to human activities*. This is a misconception because the government does not really intend to cut off human activities in the MKRNP. Instead, activities that would promote its conservation and protection are encouraged. What is prohibited are the human activities that have resulted in its degradation, such as *kaingin* farming, indiscriminate cutting of trees, indiscriminate hunting of birds and other animals and other destructive activities. This revelation therefore calls for a more focused IEC on this particular aspect in order to correct the misconception.

Table 3. Perception on the Essence/Purpose of Mt. Kitanglad Range Natural Park of the Respondents, Barangay Imbayao, 2008.

PURPOSE/ESSENCE OF MKRNP (Total respondents: 256)	F	%
1. For the protection and conservation of its forests	216	84.4
2. Off-limits to human activities	216	84.4
3. For the protection of its remaining flora and fauna	180	70.3
4. A sanctuary for endangered species of plants and animals	177	69.1
5. Off-limits to farming	133	52.0
6. Tourist Destination	100	39.1

With regards to the perceived benefits of MRKNP, Table 4 shows, the respondents perceived that the number one benefit they can get from the MKRNP is the *Assurance that the community will not experience natural and human induced disasters*, obtaining 189 responses or 73.8%. Following closely is *Improved community pride*, 178 responses or 69.5%. This is in turn followed closely by *Improved basic services delivery, such as health-care, education and water*, with 160 responses or 62.5%. Following far down below are: *Provided employment for community members* with 90 responses or 35.2%; *Improvement of community infrastructures such as roads, schools and others*, with 56 responses or 21.9%; and *Increased income from agriculture*, with a meager responses or 15%. The overall result also show low number of responses or percentages. One implication of this result is that a lot of people in the community do not see tangible community benefits from the MRKNP. This then further implies that programs for the MKRNP that are supposed to benefit the community are still wanting. Or another implication is that, if ever there were programs to this effect, it was not clear as to what benefits they could get from them.

Table 4. Perception on the Community Benefits of Mt. Kitanglad Range Natural Park by of Respondents, Barangay Imbayao, 2008.

COMMUNITY BENEFITS FROM THE MKRNP (Total respondents: 256)	F	%
1. Assurance that the community will not experience natural and human induced disasters	189	73.8
2. Improved community pride	178	69.5
3. Improved basic services delivery such as health-care, education and water	160	62.5
4. Provided employment for community members	90	35.2
5. Improvement of community infrastructures such as roads, schools and others	56	21.9
6. Increased income from agriculture	15	5.9

Aside from perceived benefits of the MKRNP, this study also looked into the perceived negative effects of the park to the community. Table 5 reveals that the respondents perceived that the top 3 negative effects of MRKNP are; first the *Loss of opportunities to do farming*, garnering 164 responses or 64.1% which is obvious, considering that most of the respondents are engaged in farming; second is the *Delays in implementing development projects due to the addition of the PAMB as added layer in the approval process*, obtaining 132 responses or 51%; and third is *Environmental degradation due to increased tourist visits* with 105 responses or 41.0%. The negative effects which few of the respondents have identified are: *Loss of indigenous culture and practices*, (24.2%); *Dislocation of the tribal members and their families*, (19.1%); and *Conflicts brought about by political infighting*, (9.8%). These low responses imply that the community does not perceive these negative effects as threats to their socio-political well-being.

Table 5. Perception on the Negative Effects of Mt. Kitanglad Range Natural Park of the Respondents, Barangay Imbayao, 2008.

NEGATIVE EFFECTS OF MRKNP	F	%
1. Loss of opportunities to do farming	164	64.1
2. Delays in implementing development projects due to the addition of the PAMB as added layer in the approval process	132	51.6
3. Environmental degradation due to increased tourist visits	105	41.0
4. Loss of indigenous culture and practices	62	24.2
5. Dislocation of the tribal members and their families	49	19.1
6. Conflicts brought about political infighting	25	9.8

From these results of the general perceptions of the respondents, as to the perceived purpose of the MKRNP, residents in Imbayao view that the park's purpose is mainly ecological; for the protection of forests, flora and fauna and as a sanctuary of endangered species. This is not very far from the stated goals of the MKRNP.

As for perceived benefits and negative effects of the MKRNP, most of the Imbayao residents view the park as affecting their livelihoods both positively and negatively. For instance, most of the respondents believed that the park will protect their community hence their livelihoods from disasters. They also view the park as an opportunity for development projects (roads, health care, education and water) to be implemented in their barangay. On the flipside, Imbayao residents also view the park as a threat to their livelihoods by way of reducing their ability to farm especially when certain parts of the park will be declared as strict protection areas. For others, they view the MKRNP as an added layer of bureaucracy that will further delay the promise of development projects to be implemented in the barangay.

This seemingly conflicting perceptions of Imbayao residents validate the lessons of many projects that link conservation and development. The community-based wildlife management (CWM) project in Tanzania, Africa, showed that conservation interests or perception can also turn to negative when communities realize the trade-offs of conservation in this case their access to wildlife and the opportunity for better incomes. Even if the overall conservation work resulted to economic benefits but once people sees that these benefits are not equally distributed in the community, people's interest in the program will also disappear (Songorwa, 1999). This lesson should be considered in the sustainable management of the MKRNP—it has to continually demonstrate to Imbayao residents that although the MKRNP has primarily ecological goals, that these goals will be pursued without compromising the economic benefits of the immediate residents.

As a strategy, the MKRNP PAMB can use trade-off analysis as a tool to constantly weigh in the dynamics of ecological and livelihood purposes of the park. The tool includes steps such as stakeholders' analysis, criteria setting for social, economic and ecological objectives, scenario identification and subjecting these scenarios to the criteria set by the stakeholders. The tool was used in the Buccoo Reef Marine Park in Tobago (Brown et al., 2000).

Age of Residents in relation to community perceptions of the purpose, benefits and negative effects of the MKRNP

Table 6 presents the perception of Imbayao residents to the purpose of the MKRNP according to their age. As shown, the respondents in all the 4 age categories consistently chose statements 1-3 which state that the MKRNP is for the protection, conservation and as a sanctuary of forests, flora and fauna. Across all age categories also, statements that are least chosen by the respondents are those that say the MKRNP is off limits to farming and human activities and that it is a tourist destination. These results imply that the respondents across all age categories agree with the ecological and conservation purposes of the MKRNP but they do not agree that the park should be off-limits to farming and human activities. They also do not agree to make the park as tourist a destination.

Table 6. Perception on the Essence/Purpose of Mt. Kitanglad Range Natural Park by Age of the Respondents, Barangay Imbayao, 2008.

PURPOSE/ ESSENCE OF MKRNP	AGE GROUP							
	Young Adults (20 yrs & below) (N=15)		Adults (21 - 39 yrs) (N=135)		Middle Age (40 – 59 yrs) (N=88)		Senior (60 yrs & above) (N=18)	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
1. For the protection and conservation of its forests	15	100	114	84.4	73	83.0	13	72.2
2. For the protection of its remaining flora and fauna	9	60.0	103	76.3	56	63.6	11	61.1
3. A sanctuary for endangered species of plants and animals	9	60.0	102	75.6	58	65.9	8	44.4
4. Off-limits to farming	7	46.7	67	49.6	52	59.1	6	33.3
5. Tourist Destination	5	33.3	55	40.7	32	36.4	8	44.4
6. Off-limits to human activities	3	20.0	51	37.8	26	29.5	5	27.8

Presented in Table 7 are the results of data analyses on the respondents' perception on the community benefits of the MKRNP as classified according to age

groups. Residents across the age categories have perceived that the MKRNP protects them against natural disasters, gives them community pride and will improve the delivery of development services in their barangay.

Table 7. Perception on the Community Benefits of Mt. Kitanglad Range Natural Park by Age of Respondents, Barangay Imbayao, 2008.

COMMUNITY BENEFITS FROM THE MKRNP	AGE GROUP OF THE RESPONDENTS							
	Young Adults (20 yrs & below) (N=15)		Adults (21 - 39 yrs) (N=135)		Middle Age (40 – 59 yrs) (N=88)		Senior (60 yrs & above) (N=18)	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
1. Assurance that the community will not experience natural and human induced disasters	11	73.3	99	73.3	70	79.5	8	44.4
2. Improved community pride	12	80.0	95	70.4	60	68.2	10	55.6
3. Improved basic services delivery such as health-care, education and water	12	80.0	85	63.0	53	60.2	10	55.6
4. Provided employment for community members	2	13.3	47	34.8	36	40.9	5	27.8
5. Improvement of community infrastructures such as roads, schools and others	5	33.3	32	23.7	15	17.0	4	22.2
6. Increased income from agriculture	1	6.7	9	6.7	5	5.7	0	0

Table 8 shows the results of the perceived negative effects of the MKRNP according to age levels. There are observed differences in the response of the residents. The young adults (20 years and below), most of them (66.7%) perceived there is environmental degradation because of increased tourist visits. This implies that young people are more concern with the environmental effects of tourism. The adults (21-39 years old) and middle age (40-59 years old) most of them consistently chose loss of opportunities for farming as a negative effect with 64% and 67% respectively. This is understandable as most of the respondents within this age bracket are engage into farming already hence their high concern for the MKRNP affecting their livelihoods. The senior (60 years old and above) respondents have *Delays in implementing development projects due to the addition of the PAMB as added layer in the approval process* as the perception with most number of responses. This implies that the elderly residents of the barangay have long been waiting for the implementation of

development services in their barangay. They perceive that MKRNP will further delay the coming of these projects and services.

Table 8. Perception on the Negative Effects of Mt. Kitanglad Range Natural Park by Age of the Respondents, Barangay Imbayao, 2008

NEGATIVE EFFECTS OF MRKNP	AGE GROUP OF THE RESPONDENTS							
	Young Adults (20 yrs & below) (N=15)		Adults (21 - 39 yrs) (N=135)		Middle Age (40 – 59 yrs) (N=88)		Senior (60 yrs & above) (N=18)	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
1. Loss of opportunities to do farming	9	60.0	87	64.4	59	67.0	9	50.0
2. Delays in implementing development projects due to the addition of the PAMB as added layer in the approval process	8	53.3	71	52.6	43	48.9	10	55.6
3. Environmental degradation due to increased tourist visits	10	66.7	58	43.0	32	36.9	5	27.8
4. Loss of indigenous culture and practices	4	26.7	37	27.4	18	20.5	3	16.7
5. Dislocation of the tribal members and their families	0	0	31	23.0	16	18.2	2	11.1
6. Conflicts brought about political in fighting	3	20.0	15	11.1	6	6.8	1	5.6

Most the literature related to the role of age as a factor that influence attitudes, perceptions and behavior towards the natural environment show that age is negatively correlated; meaning as the person increases in age the less is the concern of this person towards the environment. There are many explanations being offered by the literature but of the more popular reason is based on the opportunity to enjoy the benefits. Older people will not live long enough to enjoy the benefits of conserving natural resources (Whitehead, 1991; Carlsson and Johansson-Stenman, 2000). Howell and Laska (1991) also demonstrated the opposite that young people exhibit more concern about the natural environment.

There are several literature that also suggest another perspective on this subject matter. This is the “cohort effect” of age which looks at age as a specific generation and not as individual people. Specific age groups may have different experiences, socio-economic status, cultural identities or socialization (Vlosky and Vlosky, 1999).

In this study of the residents of barangay Imbayao, it is observed that age does not influence the perceptions of the residents with regards to the ecological and conservation purposes and socio-economic benefits of the MKRNP. Regardless of age, residents perceive the purpose of the MKRNP as sanctuary for flora and fauna and as a means to conserve forests. With regards to benefits, regardless of age, residents perceive the MKRNP to bring protection against disasters and as an opportunity improve socio-economic services to the barangay.

While age may not influence the perception of purpose and benefits of MKRNP, there are indications that age is influencing the perception of negative effects of the MKRNP. Young people exhibit more concern for the negative effects to the ecology brought by increased tourism. Middle age residents are more concern with the potential loss of farming opportunities if areas are closed for protection. While the older, senior residents are more concern with the delays in implementing barangay infrastructure because of the added layer of bureaucracy of PAMB approvals.

This observation suggests a “cohort effect” brought by age. Young people compared to the other group have more opportunity for greater environmental literacy as recent school curriculum already include a lot of information related to climate change, roles of watershed and conserving species. The generation of middle age residents share a common socio-economic status which is basically anchored on farming only. The quality of environmental literacy in the schools they attended when they were young is not as strong as the current generation. Finally, the elderly and seniors—they have aged already as residents of the barangay waiting for “development” to arrive in their community. As Imbayao is relatively isolated and far from where most development is happening, elderly residents have been waiting for a long time for electric power, roads, and modern water and health services to come to village. Hence, the seniors are more concerned with delays that the MKRNP will bring in the implementation of physical development projects.

Educational Attainments of Residents in relation to the community perceptions of the purpose, benefits and negative effects of the MKRNP

Table 9 is a tabulation of the responses of the respondents according to the levels of educational attainment of the residents. From the table, the most of the respondents with educational level of elementary, high school and college, consistently perceived that MKRNP is mainly established for ecological and conservation purposes.

All the respondents whether they are formally schooled or not, perceived that the MKRNP is for the protection and conservation of forests, endangered flora and fauna and that it is off-limits to human activities. It is worth to note that for respondents who have not received formal schooling 70% of them perceived that the MKRNP will be off-limits for farming activities. This is highest compared to the other respondents who have more formal education. This implies that among residents with limited formal education might see the MKRNP as a threat to their livelihoods which is farming.

Table 9. Perception on the Essence/Purpose of Mt. Kitanglad Range Natural Park by Educational Attainment of the Respondents, Barangay Imbayao, 2008.

PURPOSE/ ESSENCE OF MKRNP	EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT							
	College/ Vocational (N=12)		High School (N=76)		Elementary (N=118)		No Schooling (N=50)	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
1. For the protection and conservation of its forests	12	100	68	89.5	98	83.1	38	76.0
2. Off-limits to human activities	12	100	68	89.5	98	83.1	38	76.0
3. For the protection of its remaining flora and fauna	11	91.7	54	71.1	85	72.0	30	60.0
4. A sanctuary for endangered species of plants and animals	12	100	51	67.1	83	70.3	31	62.0
5. Off-limits to farming	7	58.3	35	46.1	56	47.5	35	70.0
6. Tourist Destination	7	58.3	26	34.2	47	39.8	20	40.0

Table 10 shows the perception of the respondents on the community benefits from the MRKNP as classified according to educational attainment. The results show that based on the percentages of responses from the respondents, the top 3 perceived benefits of the MKRNP are the same across all the levels of education. These perceived benefits are *Assurance that the community will not experience natural and human induced disasters*; *Improved community pride* and *Improved basic services delivery such as health-care, education and water*. This means that regardless of educational attainments—residents expect that the MKRNP will give them protection, pride and socio-economic benefits to the community.

Table 10. Perception on the Community Benefits of Mt. Kitanglad Range Natural Park by Educational Attainment of Respondents, Barangay Imbayao, 2008.

COMMUNITY BENEFITS FROM THE MKRNP	EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT							
	College/ Vocational (N=12)		High School (N=76)		Elementary (N=118)		No Schooling (N=50)	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
1. Assurance that the community will not experience natural and human induced disasters	10	83.3	53	69.7	93	78.8	33	66.0
2. Improved community pride	9	75.0	59	77.6	85	72.0	25	50.0
3. Improved basic services delivery such as health-care, education and water	6	50.0	59	77.6	66	55.9	29	58.0
4. Provided employment for community members	5	41.7	22	28.0	49	41.5	14	28.0
5. Improvement of community infrastructures such as roads, schools and others	5	41.7	10	13.2	27	22.9	14	28.0
6. Increased income from agriculture	0	0	4	5.3	7	5.9	4	8.0

Table 11 shows the perception of negative effects of the MKRNP by the respondents according to the level of educational attainment. From this data, it is observed that residents regardless of their educational attainment, perceive that the MKRNP threatens their farming livelihood and will further make it difficult to bring development projects with the new layer of PAMB review and approvals. While residents across educational levels identify the ecological values of the park, they also perceive the potential negative impacts to livelihoods and development services in their barangay. It is also worth observing in this data that residents with formal education from elementary, high school and college/vocation—a significant percentage of them (as much as 25%) also fear that the MKRNP will further erode traditional, cultural and ethnic practices in the village. This is driven by the idea that the MKRNP will bring in more tourist and will open up the community to outsiders which will increase the process of assimilation of tribal members into mainstream society.

Table 11. Perception on the Negative Effects of Mt. Kitanglad Range Natural Park by Educational Attainment of the Respondents, Barangay Imbayao, 2008.

NEGATIVE MRKNP	EFFECTS OF	EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT OF THE RESPONDENTS							
		College/ Vocational (N=12)		High School (N=76)		Elementary (N=118)		No Schooling (N=50)	
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
1.	Loss of opportunities to do farming	9	75.0	48	63.2	70	59.3	37	74.0
2.	Delays in implementing development projects due to the addition of the PAMB as added layer in the approval process	7	58.3	44	57.9	55	46.6	26	52.0
3.	Environmental degradation due to increased tourist visits	2	16.7	30	39.5	51	43.2	22	44.0
4.	Loss of indigenous culture and practices	3	25.0	22	28.9	26	22.0	11	22.0
5.	Dislocation of the tribal members and their families	3	25.0	17	22.4	20	16.9	9	18.0
6.	Conflicts brought about political infighting	2	16.7	7	9.2	8	6.8	8	16.0

Several studies have positively correlated the level of formal education to positive perceptions towards conservation programs (Gillingham and Lee, 1999; Sah and Heinen, 2001; McClanahan et al., 2005; Allendorf et al, 2006; Anthony, 2007). In terms how the level of education influences positive perceptions, one explanation offered is the idea of “environmental literacy” first espoused by David Orr. In his essay in 1992 entitled “Ecological Literacy: Education and the Transition to a Postmodern World”, Orr posits that ecological literacy will make people “appreciate something of how social structures, religion, sciences, technology, patriarchy, culture, agriculture, and human cussedness combine as causes of our (environmental) predicament.” In a study in Nepal (Mehta and Heinen, 2001) demonstrated the role of ecological literacy where residents with formal education with more access to environmental awareness programs that park managers conducted showed positive perceptions to the park.

In this study in barangay Imbayao, it is observed that residents across different levels of education perceive the MKRNP for its role to preserve ecology as well as bring various socio-economic-cultural benefits to the village. There are two possible explanations of why it seems that the level education of the residents does not influence whether they will have a positive or negative perception of the park. First, based on interviews with the network of Kitanglad NGOs, there has been a lot of community awareness building activities conducted prior to this study. This building of “ecological literacy” did not only happen in the formal education structures such as schools but also at the barangay level. These activities include festivals and village meetings about the MKRNP. Second possible explanation is that even without formal education, the residents belong to any of the major indigenous peoples in the area (Talaandig, Higaonon and Bukidnon). These groups have very high regard for the forest for their livelihood and for religious purposes. Hence, even without access to deliberate ecological literacy activities, the residents already have a positive perception towards conservation and protection of the MKRNP. This second explanation also supports the observation that residents are concern of degradation of indigenous culture as a negative effect of the MKRNP.

CHAPTER V

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusions

Barangay Imbayao is an upland village located within the buffer zone of the MKRNP. The average household size of barangay is 5 persons in a household. Thirty-nine percent (39.1%) of the residents have stayed in the barangay for 10 years. Very few of them have stayed for 30 years and more. This is explained by migration as 63% of the villagers are migrants from the Visayas. The remaining 37% are members of the indigenous groups called Bukidnons and the Talaandig. Most of the people in Imbayao have at least finished elementary education. Higher level education is difficult as there are no available schools in the village. Majority of the people are engaged in farming activity while a minority is engage in small business and farm labor.

The goals of the MKRNP as stipulated by the law are the (1) protection of biodiversity, (2) sustainable and participatory development of the communities, and (3) protection of the interests of legitimate inhabitants and honoring their customary laws. From the results, the general perceptions of the respondents, as to the perceived purpose of the MKRNP, residents in Imbayao view that the park's purpose is to mainly ecological; for the protection of forests, flora and fauna and as a sanctuary of endangered species. This is not very far from the stated goals of the MKRNP.

While there is strong perception of the ecological purposes of the park, residents also have the perception that the park will give them additional socio-economic-cultural benefits such protection against disasters, improved basic services and more infrastructure projects such as roads. Again, this is not against the intention of the establishing MKRNP, which is to bring sustainable and participatory development of the communities in the park. However, the study also documented the different perceptions of possible negative effects of the park to the community. These perceptions include loss of opportunities to do farming, further delays in delivering development projects as people perceive the PAMB as another layer of bureaucracy and finally the perception that establishing the MKRNP will encourage more tourism threatening the ecology which the park seeks to protect.

This study also investigated the possible influence of age and level of educational attainment in affecting the perception of residents towards the MKRNP. In

terms age, the study concludes that regardless of age levels, residents perceive the MKRNP as having ecological purposes that brings about various socio-economic-cultural co-benefits to the community. In terms of perceived negative effects of the park, adults and seniors lean more towards the perception of threats to livelihoods while young people lean more towards threats to the ecology brought by increased tourism.

In terms of level of educational attainment, this study concludes that regardless of education levels, residents perceive the MKRNP as having ecological purposes that brings about various socio-economic-cultural co-benefits to the community. This is attributed to the high ecological literacy of the residents brought by numerous formal and informal information dissemination activities. Residents are also members of the indigenous peoples' communities with very high regard for the forest for livelihoods and religious values.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that an intensified information and education campaign (IEC) about the MKRNP is undertaken. The IEC must focus on the essence and objectives of the protected area. Messages across age groups and educational levels must be formulated separately considering that they take on the messages differently. The management of the MKRNP must also reflect on the findings that community members in barangay Imbayao do not see any tangible benefits to them from the protected area especially in the area of livelihoods and increase incomes. Most of the perceived benefits are environmental in nature and not so much on the improvement of their socio-economic conditions. This is important since community members have traded-off their access to farm lands within the park when it was declared as park and this has to be compensated with better socio-economic services to the community.

In terms of understanding the dynamic interaction of people's perception of the natural environment and the management of protected areas, further studies can be conducted to answer questions like; what is the extent that community perception is translated to community action towards conservation and socio-economic development? What is community support in protected area management? What are the levels of this support? What are the possible determinants of increased level of community support?

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